

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

September 18, 2025
LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

Co-funded by
the European Union

LOGOS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

September, 2025

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VALBONA NATHANAILI

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Dr. Nathanaili is currently a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania, with an experience of more than 35 years in the field of academia and publication. She is a Bachelor in physics and a doctoral degree holders in the science of pedagogy, both from University of Tirana. Major areas of research over the last few years are the politics and reforms in Albanian Education System, methodology of teaching science, university pedagogy, the future of schooling and Recognition and Accreditation of Prior Learning gained after flexible learning paths. She is analyst, writers and contributor for different periodic Albanian newspaper and television outlets. Nathanaili, in collaboration with different HEIs, has been initiator and supporter of STEM national campaigns, to encourage girls to pursue careers in science, technology, engineering and math fields and promote women in those fields. Dr. Nathanaili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects.

KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUMIS

LOGOS University College

Konstantinos Giakoumis is Professor of History, Arts and Didactics at LOGOS University College, where he also leads the Faculty of Humanities and Linguistic Communication. He is a doctoral degree (Ph.D.) holder PhD from the University of Birmingham, serves on the international advisory board of Art Readings (Institute of Art Studies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and reviews for the Serbian Academy of Sciences, the University of Crete, and international journals including *Speculum* (University of Chicago Press), the *Journal of Religious History* (Wiley), and *Politics, Religion & Ideology* (Taylor & Francis). He has also served as coordinator of a number of ERASMUS+ CBHE projects (Roaming, Homo Digitalis, DiLanEdu-WB). For a Marie Curie fellowship application in 2018 he received the European Commission's Seal of Excellence. A prolific scholar, his work appears in leading journals such as *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* (Cambridge), *Turkish Historical Review* (Brill), and the *International Journal of Cultural Policy* (Taylor & Francis). His most recent book examines the Codex of the Diocese/Metropolis of Dryinoupolis and Gjirokastra (1760–1858), published by LOGOS University College Press.

ELONA KARAFILI

POLIS University

Dr. Elona Karafili is an expert in the field of economic development. She is a lecturer and researcher at POLIS University, Tirana, Albania since 2007. She holds a PhD in Urban Planning from Ferrara University and Polis University. Elona currently holds the position of the Deputy Rector of POLIS University. Her main topics of interest and expertise

include regional economic development and territorial competitiveness, which she has explored through a number of projects that focus on place-based innovation. Dr. Karafili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects. She is enthusiastic to strengthen the innovation ecosystem in Albania through fostering co-creative processes, academia–business collaboration and knowledge transfer, startup support and commercialization of research.

DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ

University of Sarajevo

Vice Rector for Quality at the University of Sarajevo and a Professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. Her research interests and teaching are focused on software engineering in biomedical and cognitive domains. She is highly motivated to learn about problem domains and committed to achieving a high level of user experience. In addition to teaching and research, she is engaged in various activities aimed at improving education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially through promoting student-centered and outcome-based learning and using software as educational content.

BLERTA DRENOFCI (CANI)

LOGOS University College

Dr. Drenofci has devoted her efforts for last 20 years at the Albanian Disability Rights Foundation, to the activities in advocacy and lobbying for disability related policy and legislation adoption and implementation and offering of supportive services for people in need throughout the country. She is an expert in the area of social policies and collaborator in the formulation of policy framework for people with disabilities in Albania. She has directed ADRF contribution in several important legal initiatives. ADRF is acknowledged as the pioneer and leader of human rights-based approach to disability and it is one in the few organizations that offer models of supportive services like mobility means, supported employment, free legal aid for people in need in Albania. Blerta has an PhD in Social Sciences and has an academic background, being a teacher of University of Tirana since 2013. She has been the leader and the author of a lot of studies in the field of social policies in and outside the country. She has been involved as a consultant in the research and policy development by several international agencies. During the years 2014-2022, she has been involved in the development of the new reform for the assessment of disability in Albania, based on international standards.

ARBANA KADRIU

South East European University

Arbana Kadriu is a Full Professor of Computer Science at the Faculty of Contemporary Sciences and Technologies, South East European University (SEEU) in Tetovo, North Macedonia. She earned her PhD in Computer Science from Ss. Cyril and Methodius

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PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

SEPTEMBER 18, 2025

Hosted by LOGOS University College

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SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Trends, Challenges and Perspectives

Logos University College, Tirana, Albania

Thursday, September 18, 2025

9.00-9.30	Registration
9.30-10.00	Open remarks
	Ilia Ninka, rector, LOGOS University College
	Gertiola Cepani, Director of Labour Market Services at 'National Employment and Skills Agency'
	Konstantinos Giakoumis, HOMO DIGITALIS Project Coordinator

TOPIC

AUTHOR(S)

OPPONENT

FIRST CONFERENCE TRACK			
Digital Competences in Higher Education and the Labour Market			
10.00-10.20	1. The Impact of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Management. Case Study: Albanian Universities During the Pandemic Period	Emira Spahaj, Edisela Mena, Malvina Hysa, Blerta Avdia	Elona Karafli
10.20-10.40	2. Barriers and Opportunities in Albanian Higher Education for Students with Disabilities: A Mixed-Methods Analysis	Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Valbona Nathaniaili	Merima Muslić
10.40-11.00	3. The Digital Employment Gap in Albania: Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education	Gertjana Hasalla	Arberore Bicaj
SECOND CONFERENCE TRACK			
Institutional Strategies and Policy Development			
11.00-11.20	4. Integrated Technical Assessment and Restoration Strategy for the "Topulli" House: Restoration Strategies, Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies	Nikolla Vesho, Panagiotis Kyriatsis, Ajla Gjoka, Lumturi Haska, Sara Ciba, Migena Gjoni, Ardis Duka, Romir Mazari	Konstantinos Giakoumis
11.20-11.40	5. The Role of MOOCs and Open Educational Resources in Higher Education: Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	Dorina Minxuri	Valbona Nathaniaili

11.40 -12.00	6. Language Technologies and Digital Humanities for Low-Resource Languages and Communities	Arbana Kadriu, Lejla Abazi-Bexheti	Blerta Drenofci (Çani)
12.00-12.20	Coffee break		
12.20-12.40	7. The Cognitive–Digital Turn in Higher Education. <i>A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio</i>	Fulvio Papadhopulli, Megi Tafaj	Nikolaos Avouris
12.40-13.00	8. Defining a Strategic Action Plan for AI in Higher Education	Nikolaos Avouris	Valbona Nathaniai
13.00-13.20	9. Institutional Policies and Strategic Directions for Advancing Digital Competencies in Higher Education	Hajdin Berisha, Agron Hajdari, Bekim Samadraxha	Flora Krasniqi
THIRD CONFERENCE TRACK The intended and attained curriculum			
13.20-13.40	10. Digital Competencies in Social Sciences – A Pilot Study. <i>From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project</i>	Valbona Nathanaïli, Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Konstantinos Giakoumis, Dušanka Bošković, Arbana Kadriu, Anisa Duka	Bujar Gallopeni
13.40-14.00	11. Enhancing Learning through Multimedia Cultural Heritage Applications: Managing Cognitive Load	Merima Muslić, Dušanka Bošković, Vensada Okanović, Selma Rizvić	Blerta Avdia
14.00-14.20	12. Integrating Digital Competencies into Higher Education Curricula. <i>A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the Homo Digitalis Project</i>	Juna Muça, Anxhela Laska, Elpiniqi Merkuri, Edvaldo Begotaraj	Emira Spahaj
14.20-15.40	Lunch		
20.00-22.00	Social Dinner and Awarding of Certificates of Participation and Presentation of Papers		

**PART ONE:
DIGITAL COMPETENCES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION
AND THE LABOUR MARKET**

ENHANCING LEARNING THROUGH MULTIMEDIA CULTURAL HERITAGE APPLICATIONS

Managing Cognitive Load

Merima MUSLIĆ*, Dušanka BOŠKOVIĆ
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Abstract

The paper presents possibilities of enhancing the education by using multimedia applications, but with respect to managing Cognitive Load (CL) linked to these applications. The case study used for evaluation is based on multimedia application of digital cultural heritage, specifically the site of White Bastion fortress in Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina. The research question is focusing on the use of Cognitive Load Theory as a cornerstone for benchmarking levels of immersion and edutainment in User eXperience (UX). In our research we would like to establish a straightforward and simple way of measuring UX in multimedia cultural heritage applications aimed for education. Being aware of limitation of such simplified approach, our objective is not to elaborate qualities and drawbacks of such applications but to provide developers with simple measure of their success. Such measurement is instrumental in comparison of different applications or different versions of an application. In addition to general aspects of usability we focus on specific objectives of multimedia cultural heritage applications: immersion and edutainment; important concepts for successful usage of multimedia in education.

Keywords: multimedia, multimedia in education, immersion, edutainment, digital cultural heritage

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DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ

Vice Rector for Quality at the University of Sarajevo and a Professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. Her research interests and teaching are focused on software engineering in biomedical and cognitive domains. She is highly motivated to learn about problem domains and committed to achieving a high level of user experience. In addition to teaching and research, she is engaged in various activities aimed at improving education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially through promoting student-centered and outcome-based learning and using software as educational content.

VENSADA OKANOVIĆ

Vensada Okanovic has finished her BSc, MSc and PhD studies at the University of Sarajevo, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, where she is a professor. Her expertise and research interests are in the fields of web and mobile applications development, software engineering, web technologies and graphics programming. She is an active collaborator of Sarajevo Graphics Group and co-author of their projects and publications.

SELMA RIZVIĆ

Professor of Computer Graphics at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Sarajevo. For 23 years she has been teaching there at Bachelor, Masters and PhD study programs. From 2005-2010 she has been engaged as well at the Sarajevo School of Science and Technology, where she established computer graphics courses and Digital Media Center laboratory. At the University of Sarajevo, she founded in 2004 the Laboratory for Computer Graphics - Sarajevo Graphics Group. It is a research group that specializes in the use of 3D technologies for the presentation of cultural heritage. The SGG research group is multidisciplinary, it includes computer graphics experts and works with archaeologists, historians, visual artists, writers, film professionals, in order to design and implement virtual cultural heritage applications which have both educational value and are engaging, entertaining and attractive at the same time.

INTRODUCTION

Multimedia cultural heritage applications bring within digital reach of wider public audience interesting and important historic sights. Through virtual visits, augmented reality and serious games users are immersed in otherwise unreachable world and educated and entertained throughout the process.

In our research we address usability factors specific for multimedia cultural heritage applications, and look beyond standard usability principles as learnability, consistency, feedback, etc. However, our objective is to develop a simple and efficient instrument to measure users' perception of the usability of multimedia cultural heritage applications. We would like to provide developers with a benchmark – “a single, standardized and summated score for analyzing and reporting usability metrics” (Sauro and Kindlund, 2005).

According to Wiberg and Jegers (2003) factor important to both entertainment and education is immersion, as a measure of absorption and engagement with the virtual multimedia environment, challenging for evaluation with the standard user testing methods. Important aspect of entertainment in educational applications is to create a motivating and successful environment for learning which introduces a new combined factor: edutainment.

Fig. 1. White Bastion fortress, Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Using multimedia in education

The integration of multimedia in education had significantly changed the way students engage with complex and diverse subjects, offering immersive and interactive experiences that traditional methods cannot provide. Multimedia enables students to see what otherwise would not be possible, either it is not existing any more, it is not reachable or not visible. In the context of digital heritage, multimedia applications play a crucial role in making cultural and historical content more accessible and engaging for a wide audience. By combining visual, auditory, and storytelling elements, multimedia tools enable deeper understanding and retention of heritage information, fostering a more meaningful learning experience.

As technological advancements continue to evolve, the use of multimedia applications in cultural heritage education has become increasingly important for promoting awareness, appreciation, and preservation of rich cultural legacies. It is especially important for cultural heritage reconstructed in multimedia applications or inaccessible to learners community due to different reasons.

Multimedia applications offer significant benefits for education, but they also introduce new cognitive challenges that can influence learning effectiveness. The concept of cognitive load refers to the amount of mental effort required to process information within working memory. When multimedia content is poorly designed or with unfriendly and complex user interface, it can overload learners' cognitive capacity, leading to reduced understanding and retention. Managing cognitive load is therefore essential for designing effective multimedia educational applications, particularly in the context of digital heritage, where historical, cultural, and visual information needs to be conveyed in a way that supports, rather than hinders, learning.

Measuring immersion and edutainment

Evaluation of user experience for multimedia cultural heritage applications has specific significance, since assessing effectiveness and efficiency is inseparable of user perception of the benefits of engagement with the application. While discussing measurement of user experience we need firstly to answer two basic questions: "What" we would like to measure, and afterwards "How" we plan to measure. Rationale for the measurement is not less important, to answer the question "Why" we get engaged in the process of measurement at all.

Measuring user experience with multimedia cultural heritage applications is linked to measuring immersion and edutainment. Weibel and Weissmath (2011) have considered spatial presence and flow as key concepts to explain immersive experiences. They concluded that immersive experiences can be divided into spatial immersion (presence) and immersion in the task (flow), examining the relation between presence and flow, concluding that these are distinct constructs. R. Paiva de Oliveira, D.C. Paiva de Oliveira and Tavares (2016) measure immersion mainly with objective of evaluating narrative of a game, and look for different dimensions of the immersion. Jenett, Cox, Cairns, Doparee, Epps, Tijs and Walton (2008) present a very thorough and detailed review on methods used to evaluate concepts of immersion, engagement, flow and presence, as concepts used to describe the perceived quality of the interaction with digital media and games. This research is addressing the question "How" to measure, and the authors emphasized the ambiguity of subjective emotional phenomena and focused on measurable objective concepts, what they call rational phenomena like the player's performance and biological phenomena: physiological measurements as galvanic skin resistance.

In the area of multimedia applications both for education and digital heritage presentation authors notice lack of evaluation tools. Methods for evaluation of multimedia applications commence with identification of attributes to be measured Botchini and Garzotto (2007), often referred to as heuristics, and classified in groups or dimensions

of evaluation. Developing an evaluation framework for multimedia cultural heritage applications is a challenging process due to involvement of multidisciplinary dimensions including: interaction and design for multimedia applications, pedagogy and cognitive theory, content related heuristics involving history, archeology, arts, and etc.

Difficulties in discussing and measuring edutainment arise from opposition between the important pedagogical aspects and aspects of importance for the entertainment part of the content presentation (Wilberg and Jegers 2003).

Edutainment is not a novel attribute in designing educational applications, but the importance of edutainment is especially recognized in the research field of serious games and digital cultural heritage presentations (Sweller, 1994). Effectiveness of these applications can be measured directly in terms of acquired knowledge. One of common misconceptions linked to multimedia material usage in education is that is effective mainly because it increases motivation and that learners are more motivated to engage with multimedia material which fosters their learning (Prinz, Kollmer, Flick, Renkl, Eitel, 2022).

Measuring entertainment and its influence on learning outcomes achievement is not a straightforward process. In assessing the edutainment influence on successful learning it is useful to include measurements which take into account Cognitive Load Theory (Leppink, Paas, Van der Vleuten, Van Gog, Merrienboer, 2013. and Kirakowaki, Corbett, 1993). The results of applying this qualitative approach in evaluating White Bastion 4D model is described in the Section 4.

The complexity of usability analysis makes usability data hard to digest and it is difficult for designers and developers to compare the relative usability of different features or products (Sauro and Kindlund, 2005). Maintaining the balance of focus in the multidisciplinary team is not easy, because of their difference in priorities. Psychologists are focused on purity of methodology with objective to reach general and standard conclusions, and computer science professionals are asking for specific and particular technical improvements (Lazar, Feng, Hochheiser, 2010). Designers and developers are looking for substantial informative feedback. For this reason, this interdisciplinary approach is sometimes misunderstood by professionals from both feeds, as they feel that on one hand it does not meet scientific criteria (psychologist) and on the other does not offer plan that is concrete enough for intervention (developers). However, we argue that combining psychological theoretical framework and research methodology with problem solving focus and IT tools is necessary for both fields to advance.

Example of a more quantitative oriented evaluation can be found work of Schrepp, Hinderks and Thomaschewski (2017) where authors have described the instrument to be used to calculate a general satisfaction score, as well as for the evaluation of products. It is a 50 items Likert-type questionnaire, which is named Software Usability Measurement Inventory - SUMI. This questionnaire is made up of five sub-scales, where each sub-scale is represented by 10 items. It has been developed to provide a standardized measurement of user satisfaction with software. The web version of the SUMI questionnaire is available and used for years by developers and academia, building up a large repository of survey results.

White Bastion 4D presentation

White Bastion is a fortress above old town of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina (see Fig. 1). In some historical moments it was a part of city walls. Archaeological excavation of the site has shown remains of various strata, dating from medieval till Austrian Hungarian period of Sarajevo past. Online application consists of 10 digital stories, 6 interactive virtual environments depicting the assumed appearances of the fortress in different time periods, as well as digitization and virtual reconstruction of artifacts found on the site during excavation, at the moment kept in the Museum of Sarajevo’s depo.

Fig. 2. White Bastion application’s structure

Digital stories are combined with virtual reality environments where users are free to explore models of the fortress, examine archaeological findings’ reconstructions and watch stories about particular details from Bastion’s history.

Cognitive load

Digital storytelling is a form of multimedia storytelling where narrative is combined with pictures, sounds and video animations. Digital stories can be educational, historical, entertaining and have wide application in education, business world, public health and healthcare, social media and libraries.

Digital story represents the kind of hypermedia in a wider context. Hypermedia is expanded version of hypertext to which multimedia elements are added. Hypertext and hypermedia are the subjects of many intensive researches in educational sciences given

their significant educational potential. Unfortunately, the results of research of hypertext efficiency on learning are not consistent (Schurer, Opitz, Schubert, 2023). There is a general consensus that processing the content of hypertext and hypermedia is very cognitive demanding, and can cause disorientation hence the cognitive overload can lead to less efficient learning. The high level of cognitive effort and possibility of disorientation can significantly reduce the state of involvement of the user. The Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) is one of today's most famous theories of educational psychology introduced in (Sweller, 1988). It contains a universal set of learning principles that result in an efficient learning environment (Sweller, Ayres, and Kalyuga, 2011). CLT is applicable to all types of content, all media and all users. This is a relatively new paradigm in psychology, the possibility of designing content in a way that it maximizes people involvement regardless of individual differences. Furthermore, on this premise CLT developed set of guidelines for instructors to follow while designing educational content. These guidelines have been validated in number of experimental research done by CLT researchers. Following the same logic and train of thought CLT researchers have started to look for ways to apply CLT instruction guidelines in education software and multimedia. Following this train of thought we can conclude that, every multimedia environment should be designed in compliance with architecture and processes of a human mind, in order to achieve the state of involvement.

For software developers this is a practical and innovative approach in designing content that will be optimal for all users. The settings and the predictions of a theory are empirically verified in a number of experimental studies (Mayer, 2001; Brünken and Leutner, 2001; Plass and Salisbury, 2002).

CLT sets the scene for creating a more efficient hypermedia in general, and hence digital stories as well. In addition, clear and operationally defined variables, from the CLT settings, are important for testing the efficiency of a hypermedia environment, including digital stories. According to the Cognitive Load Theory, the human cognitive architecture is a register of working and long-term memory (Sweller, Ayres, Kalayuga, 2011). In working memory, information that we receive from the environment, as well as information that is already stored in long-term memory, is processed. The previously acquired knowledge is stored in the form of mental schemes in long-term memory. The scheme is a cognitive construct that organizes multiple elements of information into a unique element (Chi, Glaser and Rees, 1982) Learning is defined as a process of forming a scheme. The scheme that is being formed is being processed consciously and with a significant cognitive effort.

Cognitive load represents the actual amount of working memory's resources invested in cognitive activity. Or we can say that cognitive load refers to the total amount of mental effort being used in the working memory. It depends on many factors, including material complexity, prior knowledge and motivation.

According to original CLT, the content of a particular structure and presentation mode can lead to three types of cognitive load: intrinsic, extraneous and germane.

The intrinsic cognitive load is conditioned by the complexity of the information being learned or the problem being solved. The intrinsic load level is determined by the number

and interactivity of the elements (symbols, concepts, procedures, rules, and links) that are simultaneously processed in working memory (Sweller and Chandler, 1994).

The extraneous load is unnecessary (unproductive, unconstructive, bad) load due to the design and organization of material, format, and manner of information presentation. It requires additional mental effort due to unnecessary cognitive activities that do not contribute to the adoption or automation of the scheme (Van Merriënboer and Sweller, 2005).

Intrinsic and extraneous loads are primarily determined by the characteristics of the material being taught or the problem being solved and to a certain extent by the characteristics of the person. Together, these two loads determine the total cognitive load conditioned by the material that needs to be learned or the problem that needs to be solved, what is in line with a revised version of CLT presented by Sweller, van Merriënboer, and Paas (2019) with germane load considered as “germane processing.” The load inflicted by the processes leading to the formation and automation of the scheme is the germane load. This load directly contributes to the process of learning and problem solving, as it includes work memory resources devoted to the processing of the learning material’s interactive elements. Mayer (2005) offered Cognitive theory of multimedia learning that is in its later iterations defined as a Cognitive- affective theory of multimedia learning. In this theory concepts of CLT are explained in light of multimedia context. Digital storytelling takes place in the interaction between users and computers. In order for the digital story to meet the usability criteria, it is necessary to reduce unnecessary cognitive load, adjust intrinsic load and increase the germane load. Comprehensive summary of challenges in understanding cognitive load in digital and online learning (Skulmowski and Xu, 2022) concluding that the extraneous load in online learning can have different components, and that the challenges presented demonstrate that design of digital learning environment while inducing cognitive load is increasing learning performance.

The following parts of the paper are presentation examples that lead to an increase or decrease in cognitive load.

Cognitive Load on a Macro Level

The structure of the homepage and the contents of the introduction story have the function of the organizer. The use of different organizer forms is an effective way of organizing information presented in hypermedia, which results in a decrease in cognitive load, especially for beginners (Chalmers, 2003). The choice of graphical user interfaces representing each time period is appropriate because it is clear and intuitive and contributes to the activation of prior knowledge. However, the functional and aesthetic improvements are possible, thus making the homepage more interesting and dynamic.

The user can freely browse the presentation. For example, first, they can choose the introductory module and then the Ottoman period next. However, the logic of the presentation imposes a linear sequence of movements since the modules are chronologically sorted. At the macro level, the possibility of disorientation is minimal, which is expected with a relatively small number of modules.

COGNITIVE LOAD OF DIGITAL STORIES

When the digital story is linear, the user has the ability to control its presentation. The user has the ability to stop, return and move in advance. The ability to control the presentation is an important feature of reducing intrinsic loads in dynamic multimedia presentations.

Initial scenes in videos (such as the Ottoman period) are not consistent with the content of the spoken text. Namely, the narrator explains that in one period “there were no wars or fights, nor the need to make swords or to build the fortification walls”, while the screen depicts scenes of destroyed parts of the fortress. The user is exposed to two different messages that are not congruent, but which still need to be processed and form a coherent mental model. The basic content is contained in a text spoken by the narrator. Therefore, video content can be considered redundant, and the principle of coherence is disrupted.

This kind of problem is common in the presentation. We can conclude that the cognitive load can be reduced by creating highly usable software, as well as adjusting the story content to the specific characteristics of the user. Furthermore, the principles of learning derived from the theory of cognitive load and the process model of the digital story provide guidelines for designing an efficient multimedia environment for the digital story. The digital story will be a more effective learning tool with using graphical content and spoken text rather than graphic content and written text (modality or multimedia principle).

The modality effect is mostly studied in the field of multimedia design. In multimedia, the modality effect is applied by presenting animation and narration rather than animation and text on the screen. The modality effect can be of particular importance when complex material needs to be presented in a short period of time. In this case, the presentation of animation and text can lead to a split attention effect, in which students have to divide their cognitive capacity between animation and text. The solution to this problem is to replace the text on the screen with narration, which relieves the visual channel and burdens the auditory one. In fact, the mentioned effect is a part of multimedia learning, in which the input information is presented in several forms (Mayer, 2005).

According to Kalyuga (2009) these are some of the CLT specific implications for designing situations involving multimedia:

- written text enriched with visual representations;
- presenting visualizations and appropriate textual explanations simultaneously rather than sequentially to avoid temporal division of attention;
- present connected sources of information close to each other on the screen (eg, insert text into graphics, avoid covering or separating information that must be mentally integrated for learning, design a space for guidance or feedback near the space for a friend);
- avoid irrelevant graphics, explanations, interesting but unimportant details, unimportant sounds and music, meaningless words and long text;
- use visual representations explained by the sound of the narration, not the text on the screen;
- use animated visualizations with short audio narratives rather than on-screen textual explanations;
- present static or animated visualizations with narrative only, instead of duplicating the narration with the text on the screen

RESEARCH QUESTION

Motivation for our research is to obtain reliable measure of success of multimedia digital heritage applications, especially measuring success in achieving features as edutainment and immersion. The quantitative approach in measurement of edutainment and immersion is important when assessing the level of development of the application or comparing different solutions. Developing standardized system for evaluation requires extensive data collection activities, especially when assessing multimedia cultural heritage applications. The challenge in standardization is to design a framework questionnaire adapted to specific content of a specific cultural heritage application. Inspired with the SUMI questionnaire (Kirakowski & Corbett, 1993) and possibility to build a significant database of evaluation results available for analyses we would like to develop similar instrument specific for the multimedia digital heritage applications. Important decision is how to start this process and to build a data collection for future research in this field. Our choice of White Bastion application is motivated by (1) familiarity with the application and also (2) with the results of several different evaluations of this application, including user surveys, Cognitive Load measurements and Heuristic Evaluation. We do not expect that measuring can be a solution in removing interaction flaws, not even to provide precise identification of the flaws, but this simple and efficient instrument can guide developers towards the most needed improvements in designing interaction of multimedia heritage applications. This is the reason that we do not aim to use benchmarking process as a ranking, but as being “the process of identifying and learning from good practices in other” as it is considered in the quality management field (Chalmers 2003).

MEASURING METHODOLOGY

We have decided for the self-selection of users, with emphasis on their reliability, and openness to convey negative opinions, and disclose the information on time they dedicated to interaction with the presentation. In order to ensure that the responses represent diverse cross-section of respondents and to establish validity of survey responses, we included questions for relevant demo-graphic data: age, education and computer skills (Lazar and Preece, 2001).

A. Questionnaire. First version of questionnaire was designed containing 26 items. The questionnaire was reviewed by graduate students involved in research in the field of human–computer interaction, checking the consistency and clarity of items and also the balance in evaluating main dimensions or attributes; usability, immersion and edutainment. The later influenced addition of two items to each scale: digital stories and virtual models. The questionnaire contains four sections: (1) introductory part with data for user profiling, (2) questions assessing “completeness of interaction”, (3) main part for separate evaluation of digital stories and virtual models, each made up of 3 sub-scales addressing immersion, edutainment and usability satisfaction; containing total 30 Likert items, and (4) open questions where users can express their opinion about the presentation and the most favorable and the most problematic parts. Likert scale items were defined as straightforward

statements with positive logic, repetitions were avoided. The number of items in the sub-scales were not exactly the same, the importance of immersion is highlighted with more items (6) for evaluating White Bastion Digital Stories, as opposed to importance of usability for White Bastion Digital Models represented with 7 items. Complete list of items is presented in Section discussing results.

B. Participants. The evaluation involved 40 participants. Presentations of multimedia digital heritage is intended for a broad audience, and we aimed to balance different user types regarding their professional background: engineering (n=15), history (n=15) and art (n=8); and their computer proficiency: basic and intermediate (n=18), advanced (n= 11) and professional (n=11). With respect to age participants were categorized into following groups: younger than 20 (n=5), ages 20-30 (n = 26), ages 31-50 years (n = 5), and aged older than 50 years (n = 4). It is evident that the largest group was students.

C. Procedure. The users were invited to take a tour within the White Bastion presentation and after that answer the questions summarizing their perceived experience in using the application. Not being in a laboratory under strict observation, they were expected to watch the presentation in real life context, with possibility of interruptions, discontinuity in watching, etc. The complete interaction with the presentation lasts approximately 45 minutes. Total duration of digital stories is 30 minutes, and touring the White Bastion virtual model takes in average 10-15 minutes. The users needed to spend additional 10-15 minutes for answering web based post-interaction questionnaire.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results are analyzed separately for different modes of content delivery: digital stories and interactive digital virtual models.

Table 1 Stories

Attribute	Item	Mean	Std. dev.
Edutainment	Q2 - I have learned a lot from the stories	1,65	0,66
	Q3 - I became very interested in history of White Fortress	1,98	0,97
	Q4 - I wish to learn more about historical events in Sarajevo	1,65	0,74
	Q10 - I was surprised by the fact that White Fortress had very important role through different periods	1,73	0,91
	Q12 - I would like to see more stories about historical buildings	1,60	0,67
Immersion	Q1 - I have enjoyed watching all the videos	1,70	0,65
	Q5 - The music was very pleasant	1,75	0,95
	Q7 - The narrator voice was very pleasant	1,53	0,64
	Q8 - The story about Austro-Hungarian conquest of Sarajevo was interesting	1,95	0,88
	Q11 - The introduction story was very interesting	2,35	1,17
	Q14 - Time flied fast while listening and watching the stories	2,05	0,88

User Experience	Q6 - I liked the illustrations, drawings and photos of story events	1,60	0,71
	Q9 - I like the way that Sarajevo's soldier is presented in different periods of time	1,68	0,80
	Q13 - I would recommend these stories to my friends	1,65	0,70
	Q15 - Browsing the stories and choosing their order was easy for me	2,05	1,20

Table 2 Model

Attribute	Item	Mean	Std. dev.
Edutainment	Q5 - I have enjoyed exploring the White Fortress	2,00	0,93
	Q6 - I liked the 3D reconstructions of archaeological artifacts	1,98	0,76
	Q8 - The interior of White Fortress is very realistic	2,13	0,94
	Q15-The potential to follow development and change of White Fortress is very interesting	1,73	0,68
Immersion	Q2 - I could imagine the soldiers on White Fortress	2,03	0,86
	Q3 - I almost felt like I was inside the real White Fortress	2,48	1,08
	Q9 - Time flied fast while I was walking in White Fortress virtual environment	2,25	0,87
	Q10 - The colors of the model were very calming	2,10	0,76
User Experience	Q1 - I didn't wait for the 3D model to load completely	2,40	1,46
	Q4 - Moving in White Fortress virtual environment was easy	2,28	0,93
	Q7 - I could easily notice the objects with 3D reconstructions in virtual environment	2,35	1,09
	Q11 - I could easily navigate to other parts of the presentation	2,28	0,92
	Q12 - The movement through virtual environment was hard to control	3,45	1,06
	Q13 - I felt dizzy because the model was spinning while I was walking through it	3,23	1,32
	Q14 - I have noticed that clicking on the soldier activates the video story	2,70	1,09

Visualization provides insight in assessment of answers for each specific item in the main part of the questionnaire, and grouped according the sub-scales, as presented in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

Fig. 3 Visualization of results for Digital Stories

Fig. 4 Visualization of results for Interactive Digital Model

We have devised steps to create a single metric summarizing results for the White Bastion 4D model. First step is to calculate metrics to summarize scaling data for each of 6 sub-scales, to make them more interpretable and enable comparison of the main factors: immersion, edutainment, and usability. We have explored results obtained using several typical scores defined by Sauro and Lewis (2016) and although the absolute values were different, the patterns observed when identifying the highest and the lowest values, were the same. Results obtained for the scores “Percent Agree” and “Net Promoter Score (Customer Experience Index)” are presented in Table 3. Results indicated the lowest rating (22.1%)

for usability of the Bastion's virtual models: for their experience of navigating within the virtual models, or noticing 3D models of archeological objects. We were aware of these difficulties reported in prior evaluations. It is interesting to notice that these difficulties also caused lower rating in the statements related to immersion of the Bastion virtual models.

Table 3 Summary results

Feature	Digital Stories	Bastion Models
	Percent Agree	
Edutainment	86.5%	83.1%
Immersion	80.0%	67.5%
Usability	84.4%	49.3%
	Customer Experience Index	
Edutainment	83.0%	76.3%
Immersion	75.0%	58.1%
Usability	79.4%	22.1%

The reason for the highest rating (79.4%) for usability of digital stories is obvious, since that is the part of the application where users are merely passive viewers and listeners. The more important are the difference in ratings calculated for immersion for digital stories (75.0%) and for the Bastion models (58.1%). We will not evaluate the difference arithmetically, but we can make conclusions based on possibility to identify the better of the two. Explanation for the difference is linked to usability scores and it is obvious that flaws in usability for digital stories highly affect possibility of user immersion. Further steps in aggregation of metrics would need more detailed analysis and validation against data from additional case studies to decide on appropriate weights when combining different dimensions: Usability, Immersion and Edutainment. If we decided to use uniform weights for the three dimensions, following benchmarks were calculated:

- - White Bastion Digital stories: 0.79
- - White Bastion Virtual model: 0.52

Quality of the production and the performance of digital stories resulted in achieving the higher value of benchmark.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The achieved results are in accordance with our previous experience in evaluating the same application. Regarding edutainment, we can conclude that virtual models present an entertaining way to engage users in exploring historical artifacts and to motivate them to learn more, even when accompanied with the reported issues in navigation and visibility. The compliance of the evaluation results is important for assessing our quantitative approach and possibility to develop benchmarking instrument for multimedia cultural heritage.

In order to validate our approach, we plan to continue using it as a framework for future evaluations and to build substantial data repository enabling more comprehensive research in this field. Our next step is to advertise both 4D model and the user evaluation questionnaire more publicly in order to obtain larger sample size and to enable further statistical analysis of the results. In order to address edutainment and especially immersion, the items in the questionnaire for multimedia applications has to be specific and linked directly to the content and features of the application. This is preventing design of a generic questionnaire applicable for evaluating different multimedia applications. Possibility to compare results of evaluation across different applications demands that the questionnaire is designed following proposed structure and keeping the balanced number of questions for the three main dimensions: Immersion, Edutainment and Usability.

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Digital competencies in higher education : trends, challenges and perspectives : proceedings of international scientific conference / ed. Valbona Nathanaili, Elona Karafili, Blerta Drenofci (Cani), Konstantinos Giakoumis, Dušanka Bošković, Arbana Kadiu. - Tiranë : Kolegji Universitar Logos, 2025.

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The responsible use of Artificial Intelligence is essential for fostering innovation and advancing digital competencies in higher education.

PROF. ILIA NINKA

The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education is about more than technology. It is about developing university-level strategies and adequate national and regional policies to support digital transformation. Albanian Higher Education Institutions have not yet developed an ethical framework for the use of ChatGPT and similar AI applications.

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The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education it is aligning universities with the labour market and forging strong partnerships between higher education institutions and employers.

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Digital transformation is no longer a future aspiration. It is a current imperative.

PROF. DUŠANKA BOŠKović

... with vision, with cooperation, and with determination, we can ensure that AI serves not just technology, but learning. Not just efficiency, but wisdom.

PROF. NIKOLAOS AVOURIS

Altogether, the case-studies in this volume trace a roadmap for higher education in the Western Balkans that amalgamates tradition and innovation, strives to pursue equitable access to digital opportunities, and positions regional universities as active contributors to Europe's wider digital transformation.

PROF. KONSTANTINOS GLAKOUMIS

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